

THE SILENCE OF BLACK FEMALE VOICES IN THE COURSE OF LEARNING ENGLISH LITERATURE IN SOUTH AFRICAN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract

This article explores patriarchal supremacist content in English secondary school Literature in postcolonial South Africa. In the course of colonization and Bantu Education, South African women, particularly Blacks were excluded in matters of education. They did not only endure racial, sexist, cultural, and other gendered-based atrocities in their societies and homes, they also suffered politically, economically, and intellectually. That made them more apprehensive than white women. For millennia black women, in particular, were treated as nurturers, caregivers and homemakers who were regarded as weak and dependent. Much of what secondary school literature, read in English classes, is written by males and follows a male protagonist. If women texts are involved, women are [were] portrayed differently from males, viewed as less capable or less significant. Although SA democratic constitution (Chapter 2) prescribed that everyone has a right to expression, in which everyone shares human rights, such as equality and freedom; black South African women still experience inequalities and lack of resourcefulness in the academic literary world. While women are the broad targets of myriad inadequacies and appalling atrocities in SA and have tried to raise their plights scholastically through literary writings and movements, they are deprived of chances to share these experiences in the literature that is scholastically acknowledged in secondary school Literature. As a result, this study examined the gender representation in English texts, read in SA secondary school Literature, regarding women representation in English first additional language (EFAL) Literature set-works in post-apartheid South Africa from 2009–2019 using a quantitative approach. Black Feminism Theory, which advocates equal representation of sexes, undergirds this study.

Keywords: literature, gender, black feminism, intersectionality, English first additional language.

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1. Introduction

It is no secret nor a provocative assertion, that men's voices, primarily white, European, have prevailed throughout history. Black South African women writings are not an exception of exclusion by a dominant racist and patriarchal literary world before, during and after apartheid in South Africa (SA). This impropriety was also globally practised to silence Black women voices by the dominant patriarchal and colonial rule. Although "South African citizens tried to unite and raise their voices through literary writings, movements, campaigns and documentaries and other artistic expressions" [1]. They have never been passive victims of their many oppressors [2], yet the existence of numerous black female writers is still overlooked in the literary world. Besides, female authors remain back-benched when it comes to gaining literary prestige [3, 4]. But people who have intersecting identities (race, gender, education level, socioeconomic status, sexual orientation) are mostly women. [5] notes women's voices can be heard if the disproportionate rate, at which they experience patriarchal oppression, is recognized and understood. However, this will be possible to recognize the voice of authority, truth, and individualism.

This study examines the extent, to which male-dominated literature manifests itself in the English curriculum. Drawing on Black feminist theory, the study focuses on in South African sec-

ondary school Literature for grade 12 English first additional language (EFAL). Central to the analysis in this study is the argument that infestation of patriarchy and white supremacy in literature has been promoted at the expense of Black women writings, which have been silenced for a long time. The mandates by United Nations 2006, Millennium Development Goals (2000–2015) and supporting SA statutes that emphasize women and girls' empowerment is failing, since educational institutions are less responsive to the needs of women, particularly of black women in literature, read in secondary schools.

Frameworks that advanced under “feminist theory” sought to abolish the system of patriarchy in exchange for equality amongst sexes through Suffrage and Emancipation [6]. Feminist theory is currently seen as spreading in “productivity, diverse intellectual and political assemblage that grows through imaginative interdisciplinary work and critical political engagements about the world” [7], Black feminism, which was formerly called Womanism or Afro-Feminism has received global recognition “to make demands for equality with men in society” [1]. And above, Black feminism in the classroom or Black feminist pedagogy that centres on the research, study, and development of Black women and girls [8] and their standpoints and [9] thus legitimizes the daily experiences and identities of Black women [10]. It intends to promote activism from, by, with, and for Black women and girls as opposed to Eurocentric patriarchal curriculum [11]. It thus critically assesses the patriarchal edifice of traditional education that serves White elite, aiming to create educational experiences that respect and utilize the standpoints of Black women because it understands patriarchy through an examination of the social constructions of race, nationality, culture, gender, sexuality, and class [11], letting them develop new interpretations of the traditional curriculum to enhance their consciousness through a critical societal analysis [11]. South African societies have evolved, and it continues to experience literal change every day. The canon that was taught between 1948 and 1990 cannot be glorified now. South African classrooms [are] were infested with male-orientation of the school subjects and the existence of patriarchal power relations and inequality [12–14]. This study concedes with other researchers that such inaccessible power realms in the official school subjects may be addressed by employing feminist pedagogy [15] by guiding and empowering especially the newly-qualified teachers on how to implement active learning, activist projects, and feminist assessment practices, to break the cycle of the male-dominated, hierarchical pedagogies.

In SA women are the broad targets of appalling atrocities in including sexual violence, domestic violence, workplace abuse, historical specificity, toxic masculinity, femicide, and so on. If the country were unbiased, it would offer women platforms to share their experiences in a way that their literature can be scholastically acknowledged. This paper concedes that the inclusion of Black feminist pedagogy frees the minds of Black women and Black girls, and the minds of others about Black women and Black girls, [16–18]. Literature, written by women, is capable of transmitting gender-based knowledge on women lives and approaches to their problems solving and acknowledgements, which are now male-dominated and dangerous to societies. It is vital to bring awareness to secondary school children since they are in trouble. The purpose of all bringing learners' consciousness about patriarchal oppression raises awareness of women oppression in the teaching-learning environment. It then helps learners, both boys and girls, to experience and value marginalized voices of women perspectives, realities, knowledge, and needs [19].

Therewithal, the current millennials cannot be taught the same canon that was taught between 1948 and 1990, their needs and challenges are different. If the same texts and names are read over and over again, whether they are patriarchal or matriarchal, it undermines other writers' literary contribution. [20] however, warns that misconceptions of categorizing every piece by women as feminist even though it is for social order not articulating feminist aspirations weaken the very foundations of feminism. In the same vein, [7] argues that feminist theory is not only about women; it is about the world, engaged through critical intersectional perspectives through the tool's Intersectionality, interdisciplinarity, and the intertwining of scholarship and activism.

In contrast, it cannot be denied, that although the democratic state of SA, streamlining of the previously fragmented and segregated education and curriculum under the apartheid regime is acknowledged, Black women, who are [were] the main target then, who suffered triple marginal-

isation of race, social class and sexism are still neglected [21] and identity crisis still escalates [1]. [22] advises that upholding the needs of the White elite by the curriculum must be discouraged. [23] coined the term of Intersectionality to rearticulate concerns about black female marginality. Intersectionality has been used in a variety of different ways by different scholars, as an analytical framework for social justice [22] and an approach and a way of framing interactions [22]. It is not only about multiple identities but is about rationality, social context, power relations, complexity, social justice, and inequalities [24] Gender, feminist, and intersectional approaches offer critical analyses of how people experience privilege and marginalization in private and public contexts based on their gender, race, social class, sexual and gender orientations. These critical approaches like [25] said they are.

- (a) The framing of gender as systemic social stratification and inequalities,
- (b) The application of feminist perspectives to research and praxis as a way to highlight and change power disparities in private and public spheres, and
- (c) The application of Intersectionality perspectives to examine and redress social inequities, privilege, and oppression, particularly for historically marginalized individuals. In sum,

“A Black South African feminist criticism as a method of engaging with Black, women-authored texts, takes as its point of departure the intrinsic worth of a Black woman – shaped by oppressive forces, such as slavery, apartheid, colonialism – sitting down to write and producing a text from her uniquely gendered, classed, and racialized position within Black South Africa and its diaspora. Whether fiction, autobiography, or poetry, such work should be approached as potentially containing insights and perspectives not available elsewhere” [26].

1. 1. Gender representation secondary school Literature

Although gender will always be spoken of in English classrooms, its misconceptions can divide a classroom in seconds and create a rivalry between boys against girls [27], if literature, read from the two parties, men, and women, is not balanced. According to [26], literature is the core of language curriculum. However, the catalysts of social change in literature who are teachers are often given curriculum that is gender misrepresented. The canon exists for a reason – making intentions of literature good. However, the exceptionally male canon is limiting [27].

Teachers are the figures should uphold principles of social justice and human rights than be carriers of sexist supremacist education. Literature selected should conscientize teachers about patriarchy orders that rise against women emancipation. This can help learners, “both boys and girls to experience and value marginalized voices of women perspectives, realities, knowledge, and needs” (Rose, 1989. Globally, educational systems invest heavily in the expectation that literary reading in the classroom may teach students some social, human, and cultural values [28].

According to Eagleton [21], “literature” is a highly unstable affair as it may be linked to changing social circumstances. Circumstances have changed now, what is learned in the classroom must be connected to learners’ lives. If there is no explicit mention of women stories in the curriculum, created for a democratic program, then the curriculum does not cater for principles of National curriculum statement (NCS), which must apply redress and transform the past injustices. “If the goal of education is to liberate, decolonize the minds of racialised and gendered youth, then it is crucial for teacher education programs to include the educational scholarship of Black women since they were the most oppressed and undermined.” They are the ones, found at the crossroads of race, colour and gender issues, creating marginalization. Besides, while women are the broad targets of myriad inadequacies and appalling atrocities in SA, including sexual violence, domestic violence, workplace abuse, historical specificity, toxic masculinity, femicide, and unfair treatment in general, they are not offered a chance to share these horrendous experiences in the literature that is scholastically acknowledged to teach girls of their stories [18, 29]. [26] establishes that a typical high school curriculum does not include many female protagonists, most students read mainly about the male point-of-view. If students are reading mainly about the male point-of-view, obviously they are not reading about the female point-of-view. A more balanced curriculum in schools where both male and female characters are represented, so that neither males nor females are silenced [26], can be transformative to individuals and society.

Grade twelve, commonly known as matric or the National Senior Certificate (NSC), is the main school-leaving certificate in SA. For EFAL studies, grade twelve Literature paper comprises poems, short stories, novels, plays and other literary texts like autobiographies, folklore, myths, essays, studied for enrichment purposes. Department of basic education (DBE) prescribes 8 short stories, 10 poems, novels and plays for Literature studies and assessment. The focus of this study is the literary texts, selected for the period from 2009 to 2020.

As mentioned previously, the SA National Curriculum Statement (NCS) is based on principles, such as redress, social transformation, human rights, inclusivity, environmental and social justice. Number one NCS principle ensures that educational imbalances of the past are addressed and that equal educational opportunities are provided for all sections of the population. During the apartheid era, the fostering of gender inequality in education was stereotypical [30], and substantially submerged black women's position in society, hence this study focused on women versus men representation in EFAL Literature. So, these principles were not upheld to empower black women, especially in literature.

The aim of the study was to explore the gender representation in the selected South African grade 12 literature set-works. It sought to determine the frequency level of gender representation in SA secondary school literature between the male and female writers.

2. Methodology

This study employed a quantitative method, which seeks to quantify the level of differences in a specific phenomenon [31]. This was followed by descriptive design, which intends to provide a relevant representation of traits in a particular situation to fulfill one or more of its objectives, which are to discover new meaning, to describe what exists, and to determine the frequency, with which something occurs, and to categorize information [32]. The research method and design accord with the present study as the study seeks to quantify the variety of school literature authors based on gender. Additionally, the study seeks to determine the frequency level of gender representation in SA secondary school literature, which is aligned with the objectives of the above-mentioned design.

The study further adopted a systematic sampling technique, which refers to a probability sampling, which advocates that every entity in the population has an equal chance to be comprised in the sample [33]. This sampling technique is relevant for this study since every school literature author within English discipline has equal opportunity to be included in the sample, in that, 20 authors were selected for this study. Data was further collected from secondary sources, which refer to the existing information that is appropriate to accomplish the purpose of the situation being studied [26]. For this reason, the 20 sampled literature authors serve as the existing information that is relevant to fulfill the study objectives.

The study adopted descriptive analysis, which seeks to answer questions about “who, what, where, when, and to what extent.” This type of analysis further seeks to ascertain variation in populations as well as recognising a socially significant phenomenon that is previously under-recognised [34]. This is compatible with this study because gender representation found to be less noticeable as a discrimination element in the school literature discipline. Also, the study used measures of relative frequency type of descriptive statistical analysis for data analyses. This type of analysis assesses how frequently does a particular entity occurs in the data in relation to the total number of entities for that variable. This may be conveyed in ratios, rate, proportions, or percentages [35]. This study examines how frequently does a particular gender occurs in school literature using ratios where possible.

3. Results

Tables 1–8 below present Literature, prescribed for EFAL from the focal year 2009 to 2020. The tables present results of two categories from 2009 to 2017 and then from 2018 to 2020 (the year the study was conducted). Literary texts, which are currently read, were changed in 2018. The policy on renewing Literature for SA schools is not clear. Sometimes Literature takes stays long in the curriculum.

3. 1. Presentation of literature, selected and prescribed for EFAL from 2009 to the time of the study (2020)

Table 1

Poems selected from 2009 to 2017

Title of the poem	Author	Gender of the author	Period studied
A prayer for all my Countrymen	Guy Butler	Male	2009–2017
An elementary school classroom in a slum	Stephen Spender	Male	2009–2017
Auto wreck	Karl Shapiro	Male	2009–2017
Cheetah	Charles Eglinton	Male	2009–2017
Death be not proud	John Donne	Male	2009–2017
Let me not to the marriage of true minds'	William Shakespeare	Male	2009–2017
Mementos, 1	W.D. Snodgrass	Male	2009–2017
On his blindness'	John Milton	Male	2009–2017
The birth of Shaka	Oswald Mbuyiseni Mtshali	Male	2009–2017
The Serf	Roy Campbell	Male	2009–2017

Table 2

Short stories read from 2009–2017

Title of the short story	Author	Gender of the author	Period studied
The Sisters	Pauline Smith	Female	2009–2017
The Soft Voice of the Serpent	Nadine Gordimer	Female	2009–2017
Manhood	John Wain	Male	2009–2017
The Luncheon	W. Somerset Maugham	Male	2009–2017
Relatives	Chris van Wyk	Male	2009–2017
The Coffee-cart Girl	Es'kia Mphahlele	Male	2009–2017
The Dube Train	Can Themba	Male	2009–2017
The Secret Life of Walter Mitty	James Thurber	Male	2009–2017

Table 3

Poems selected from 2018–2020

Poem	Author	Gender	Period studied
Death	Anonymous	–	2018–2020
Still I rise	Maya Angelou	Female	2018–2020
Everything has changed	Mzi Matola	Male	2018–2020
Spring	Gerard M Hopkins	Male	2018–2020
Poem	Barolong Seboni	Male	2018–2020
Mid-term break	Seamus Heany	Male	2018–2020
To learn how to speak	Jeremy Cronin	Male	2018–2020
Captive	Francis Carey Slater	Male	2018–2020
Alexandra	Mongane Wa Serote	Male	2018–2020
Sonnet 18	William Shakespeare	Male	2018–2020

Table 4

Short stories selected from 2018–2020

Title of short story	Author	Gender	Years studies in schools
A chip of glass	Nadine Gordimer	Female	2018–2020
Village people	Bessie Head	Female	2018–2020
The new tribe	Buchi Emecheta	Female	2018–2020
The doll's house	Katherine Mansfield	Female	2018–2020
Transforming moments	Gcina Mhlophe	Female	2018–2020
The fur coat	Sean O'Faolain	Male	2018–2020
The last breath	Sam Kahiga	Male	2018–2020
Next door	Kurt Vonnegut	Male	2018–2020

Table 5

Novels selected from 2009–2017

Title of novel	Author	Gender	Years studied in schools
To kill a mockingbird	Harper Lee	Female	2009–2017
Grain of wheat	Ngũgĩ wa Thiong'o	Male	2009–2017
Lord of the flies	William Golding	Male	2009–2017

Table 6

Novels selected from 2018–2020

Title of novel	Author	Gender	Years studied in schools
Cry, the beloved country	Alan Paton	Male	2018–2020
Strange Case of Dr. Jekyll and Mr. Hyde	Robert Louis Stevenson	Male	2018–2020

Table 7

Plays selected from 2009–2017

Title of play	Author	Gender	Years studied in schools
Nothing but the truth	John Kani	Male	2009–2017
Romeo and Juliet	William Shakespeare	Male	2009–2017

Table 8

Plays selected from 2018–2020

Title of play	Author	Gender	Years studied in schools
My children! My Africa!	Athol Fugard	Male	2018–2020
Shakespeare 2000 Macbeth	WG Saunders	Male	2018–2020

4. Discussions

Based on data of prescribed Literature texts data above, important points can be interpreted on how gender equality is represented.

The study found that there is no adequacy of female voices in the EFAL selected literary texts. Literature seems to prevail strongly on male categories. The implication that the degree of sexism in current EFAL curriculum is significant – gender representation according to ratios of women to men writers in prescribed grade 12 Literature from 2009 to 2020 shows the following, *poetry*=1.38 (where 1 is anonymous), *short stories*=7.9, *novels*=1.5 and *plays*=0.4.

This revelation confirms the study by [26] that there are limited texts at the secondary level curriculum that include positive representation of genders. She further advises that unequal representation of gender in the Literature can discourage learners to equally accept or appreciate both men and women's viewpoints, which is harmful.

A disproportionately small number of female authors appear in the prescribed works, which prove that the EFAL Literature content is limited to male writers. Although some authors claim that the canon has “overall literary quality, lasting significance, and a distinctive style that is worthy of study” [36], if it is overly dominant with male voice only, it is limiting learners to women's insights. By not acknowledging women, educators are silencing their voices both in the classroom and out [37].

The prescribed works from 2009 to 2017 are expanded to European and American literature. If it is women, it is the same popular women writers – for example, Maya Angelou, Nadine Gordimer and Gcina Mhlophe, more contemporary female writers are not counted, let alone South African ones. This study is in line with [38] that the canon, which was prescribed in 2016 for the young people, included texts that have been around since the 17th century.

The exclusion of women in the drama genre is evident in the prescription that is male-only. The form of exclusion is prevalent in both categories, for the previous selection and the Current Literature. Thus, using only male-written texts is in a way saying SA black women are not available, which is ridiculous. The SA black woman has been subjected too much that can be shared with the world, especially the way she is marginalised and subjugated for a long time.

This is in line with [26] that black women have been oppressed but there is plenty they want to share through their literature. Further expounds that voices of Black women “criticises both racist and sexist hegemony and also condemns all forms of patriarchy, which denigrate and dehumanise women.” Like the Black African American who suffered in both the colonial and slave system and her black male counterpart, the SA faced the similar hardships of colonialism, apartheid, and male oppression. And these exclusions on SA black authors continue to hammer them down.

No attempt is made to represent SA women poets in both categories, let alone black ones. The only poet, registered in the prescription, is African American Maya Angelou. The results further show that although Literature texts chosen are local, regional, or international, it is still about popular, who started writing before apartheid, contemporary ones are ignored. This is in line with [39] that newer texts provide insights to the 21st-century conflicts of our youth and scaffold upon the issues, discussed in older texts. To create change in the way texts are taught, the curriculum must be changed.

Collectively, now literature from three genre selections counted thirty-four (34), male authors, to nine (9) female authors. The most unfair representation in the study showed that zero Black SA women writers were selected for poetry, novel and drama sections between 2009 and 2020. The study [40] also proved that most course novel selections include few woman writers and even fewer texts that include strong female protagonists.

In summary, this study confirms the findings from an examination of the literature curriculum of one high school in Ohio by [41] that (i) the inclusion of women writers had not seen as much progress as the inclusion of minority writers in school literature, (ii) the short story unit for women writers were used less than male writers; (iii) the anthology of poetry, used at this school, still favoured men over women, but it includes more minority voices; (iv) male authors from the United States made up the bulk of the novel offerings and (v) no female author is available for instruction.

The study explored the selected literature set-works for the grade twelve level. Other studies in the future may investigate the experiences of the female teachers themselves on the teaching of the prescribed works. The study might guide the Department of education in South Africa and elsewhere on the selection of literature set-works in other grades.

5. Conclusion

This paper has presented a convincing evidence of a difference in male and female literary texts representation in EFAL in postcolonial SA. The findings sufficiently pronounce that promotion of male and white authors is still elevated in a selection of secondary school literature in EFAL. The solution to introduce secondary school children to the equal readership of both genders instead of no women writings at all is proposed to deprecate sexism, inequality, and patriarchy. Progress towards changing the imbalance should be measured both qualitatively and quantitatively in consideration to affirm to the values of human dignity, equality, and freedom. This is line with [42] that curriculum content to promote gender equality and empowerment of women needs to be fostered.

Literature teaching is best positioned to address the dangers of discrimination of gender, which for now has been unsuccessful. The study, therefore, concludes that exclusion of black women writers in EFAL curriculum in democratic SA still promotes sexist and supremacist curriculum, locally failing post-1994 legislation for equalizing gender in the EFAL curriculum reforms and the United Nations Millennium Declaration to combat forms of discrimination against women.

This article, therefore, emphasizes a balanced gender representation through a radical transformation on:

- Inclusion of black female writers in SA secondary school Literature;
- Increased opportunities for scholarship in feminist teacher training and teacher education.

The selection and teaching of Literature are not only about the writers but “What must be dealt with before something is done about teaching black literature is the teacher himself” [43].

This study exerts Black Feminism Theory to show that the involvement of women literature in secondary schools is of supreme importance for an all-inclusive social transformation. It believes that it is possible to recover strong, creative, and Black female voices that have been silenced for

millennia and also introduce contemporary creative voices to teach young boys and girls the values to appreciate women writing and teachings.

Conflict of interest

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